

DESIGNING THE (RE)CONTEXT: STOLEN GOODS (STOCKETUS)

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses my work, *Stolen goods (Stocketus)* from 2017 for ensemble, digital electronics and ‘pile of loudspeakers’.¹ The work was designed to juxtapose acoustic musical instruments and the loudspeakers (and microphones) that are so often used to project performances to the audience. By structuring the composition around the insertion of a descending time delay (going down from five to zero seconds over the duration of the work), a performance of the work explores different sonic interactions between the ensemble and the loudspeakers, for instance, creating echoes, rhythmical patterns, or simple phasing effects. In my research I am interested in how the use of technology operationalizes the performance context as a musical element rather than as a frame for a concert. Amplification technology can recontextualize musical performances and the use of music technology for this work was designed with this recontextualization in mind. The paper will address both aesthetic as well as practical considerations, e.g. notation and synchronization of the score, electronics and performers, and finishes with plans for future works.

1. INTRODUCTION

Earlier in my career I had many opportunities to work as a music technologist, specifically in the field of live sound reinforcement.² I mainly focused on performances of 20th century avantgarde electroacoustic works, that are usually supported by amplification systems either to enhance acoustic balances or to project (live) electronic sound sources. I have since segued into an academic career focusing my research on this specific topic. I remain fascinated by the combination of instrumental and loudspeaker sources and the challenges and wonders it provides within acoustic spaces but also in our perception, as often the sound we hear does not emanate from the instrument we

see but from a loudspeaker on a corner of the stage. At the same time amplification systems play a large role in contextualizing music for instance by allowing music of small ensemble in large venues for large audiences, or for symphony orchestras to perform outside of the specific acoustic conditions of concert halls (e.g. on an outdoor stage).

During my doctoral studies (until 2013) I considered many different approaches of designing experiments that take these elements of perception and contextualization into account. But the first real opportunity to do this came in 2017 when ensemble *decibel new music* commissioned and supported me to create and perform a work exploring this topic. The research question in this iteration was very much a *how* question: how can I design a system to musically explore the interactions set out above? Moving forward from this question, in the future, different research questions may be explored.

As such the work described in this paper is not the outcome of a somewhat linear composition process but the first in a few iterations around an experimental system of performers, microphones, delay lines, amplifiers, and loudspeakers as well as, of equal importance, a score that allows all these parts to synchronize.

Figure 1. Initial design sketch for the performance system.

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¹ A brief introduction to and recording of the work are available on Australian public radio (ABC) New Waves Podcast: <https://www.abc.net.au/classic/programs/new-waves/decibel-electronic-concertos-act-1/9361976>

² Because of the autobiographical nature of the research described in this paper, it is written in the first person.

2. STOCKETUS

Stolen Goods *Stocketus* was a commission by decibel new music, the Australian new music ensemble at the time based in Perth, led by Professor Cat Hope.³ The work created for six musicians (five acoustic instruments and one electronic performer) and a ‘pile of loudspeakers’. The work’s electroacoustic concept was shaped around the delay process, with a five second delay that would gradually reduce to zero over the duration of the work.

Initially the concept for the work was an installation/designed soundscape, with a big pile of loudspeakers in the middle of a gallery space and performers and audience on opposing sides (fig. 1). When the work was ultimately performed it took place on a traditional stage and for that occasion, we set-up a number (a ‘pile’) of loudspeakers center stage with the performers in a U shape around it (see fig. 3). Ensemble decibel new music’s scoreplayer⁴ (an iPad-based scrolling score player and creation environment [1, 2]) was used as a score as well as a way to sync to the changing delay times which were realized using MAX/MSP. Microphones transduced the sounds from the instruments (flute, clarinet, viola, violincello, percussion) which were mixed into a single signal that was fed through the delay process and into the pile of stacked loudspeakers, with the sixth performer realizing the electronics. The pile of speakers was given its own voice by emanating a soundscape that was created applying granular synthesis using, unrecognizable, recordings of rehearsals of the work. This soundscape was playing as a prelude while the audience entered the room to metaphorically, give the loudspeakers their own voice. It played throughout the piece loosely improvised by the electronic performer, in response to graphical cues in the score.

2.1 Concept

The concept behind this setup served two purposes, firstly, liberating the loudspeakers, so crucial for so many canonical works, from the dark corners of the stage, and so moving away from the typical sound staging. Secondly, the shifting delay times, over the course of the work, change the perceived relation between the instrumental sound and the loudspeaker sound. A five second delay, is rather long and relating the initial and the delayed sound to each other in a rhythmical way is challenging and somewhat estranging. The composition explores this space with clear incidental sounds, for instance a stroke of single bell, which is echoed in the loudspeakers five seconds later, doubled by the clarinet, and again by the strings instruments another delay period later. By and by the interaction becomes more musical and rhythmical, not unlike a slow *hoquet*. That particular element returns in the work’s name: *Stocketus* is a combination of Louis Andriessen’s seminal work *Hocketus* (1976) and *Stockie* an obscure nickname for Karlheinz Stockhausen, who is well-known for original work using tape delays, particularly in *Solo* (1967) [3]. *Stolen goods* refers to the nature of delay systems (notably echoes), stealing a sound and releasing it a while later, but also the nature of music creation, borrowing (or standing

in shoulders) of earlier music makers. This notion popped up in many facets of the work, for instance in its duration which was 273 seconds (more popularly known as four minutes and thirty-three seconds).

3. BACKGROUND

The role of loudspeaker amplification in avantgarde music has been of interest to several authors [4-6]. Pertinent here is Simon Emmerson’s [7] list of functions of amplification (table 1). Elsewhere [8] I have argued that such functions can be understood along a continuum of relative amplification levels. Subtle balancing requires lower amplification levels in comparison to intentional loudspeaker distortion or generating feedback.

Function	Example
Balance	Fixing Acoustic imbalances
Blend	Integrating timbres
Projection	Zooming in/Intentional dislocation
Perspective	Zooming out/ dislocation of space and time
Coloration	Intentional Distortion
Resonance	Intentional Feedback

Table 1. Simon Emmerson's six functions of loudspeaker amplification

Similarly, a continuum of relative runtime differences between acoustic source and amplified (loudspeaker) source can be considered. On a level almost outside of our perception there is an interesting phenomenon occurs: sound in its transduced form as an analogue electronic signal travels roughly a million times faster than sound in air. Consequentially, even though our perception is very well able to fuse what we hear with what we see, including for instance acoustic reflections arriving at different times, the misalignment of time is a given in electro acoustic music.

In sound system design and engineering small amounts of time delay can be introduced to realize subtle time alignment between different loudspeaker systems [9]. Time delays in sound system design can also be applied to delay the loudspeaker sound somewhat with respect to acoustic sources on stage, making use of the precedence (or Haas) effect to support localization of on-stage sources, from an audience perspective.

In an ideal world I would aspire to replicate, in the context of a concert, an elegant experiment described by Lewald and Guski [10]. To learn more about auditory visual integration they used led lights and sound sources at different distances away (between 1 and 50 meters), in an outdoor setting. Participants were asked to press one of two keys, depending on whether the sound or the light was perceived first. The outcomes presented in that publication suggest that there is an ‘Horizon of Simultaneity’ where the sound and light stimuli are perceived synchronously up to around a distance of 20 meters, however the nature of crossmodal perception (i.e. stimuli appear as one unified event rather than two different percepts) may extend this horizon to greater distances, and perhaps as much as 100

³ <https://decibelnewmusic.com/>

⁴ <https://decibelnewmusic.com/decibel-scoreplayer/>

milliseconds in temporal disparity. The work discussed in this paper is a first attempt to explore this idea of auditory visual integration in the complexity of acoustic and loud-speaker sources and in the context of (live) musical performance.

4. CREATING THE SCORE

4.1 Preparation

Firstly, I should mention that even though I have worked as a music technologist and musician for three decades this is the first formal composition I have created and the project both challenged my existing skill sets as well as supported the development of new skills.

The scrolling score environment provides a great framework to create a work like this. I used a mix of traditional notation and graphics, leaving room for the performers to choose pitches and timbres while the timing was stricter to work with the delay system. When I began drafting the score I used a DAW, to also allow for the creation of a click track, should this be necessary. For the greatest part of the work, I opted to use traditional rhythmic notation with varying meters and tempo to make the inevitable acceleration caused by the delay system more gradual. However, this was at odds with the systematic linear reduction in delay time, which I consequentially made more gradually, reducing the delay time in a series of steps, of varying size. This change resulted in the creation process becoming more of a puzzle for which the pieces needed a design approach to come together. For most parts of the work, I wanted the source and delayed notes to be working in rhythmical time, which in theory, would allow me to use compositorial devices such as canons and fugues.

An interesting side effect of this rather rational and linear approach to meters and tempi in the score is that it allowed me, perhaps even encouraged me, to be very liberal with assigning rhythmical and pitch values.

Figure 2. Page 12 of the scrolling score, tempo =277, delay 1302 milliseconds. Top to bottom: Electronic part (granular soundscape), Vln., Vc., Bass, Bcl., Perc., delay response.

For instance (figure 2) a section with half and whole notes played on the instruments are sounding in canon through the delay system, the duration of one bar later. The lowest

system shows the echoes of the drum roles played on the one but last system. The pitch values and rhythms were simply improvised on a keyboard and recorded as midi data.

4.2 A Rational Path to Chaos

Using an increasingly complex spreadsheet (table 2) I optimized the size of the descending steps to be maximally useful using common (as in, somewhat executable) meters. With a combination of guesswork and mathematics I derived the delay times for each part with one part on one page. Each of 21 pages, conveniently 273 is divisible by 13, had the same duration of 13 seconds, to realize a consistent scroll. The delay times were matched to BPM and meter in a way that would allow for a reasonable number of either bars or notes per page. A BPM greater than 300 would be very problematic to play and for the final two pages I had to switch to a different notation strategy.

4.3 Fast-paced Notation

Initially I borrowed from Jazz, using rhythmical Big Band figures or patterns. To increase the information density on each page every individual quarter note in the score was to be performed as a predefined 16th or triplet figure of four (or three) notes. In rehearsals this proved to be cumbersome and after that I ‘stole’ once more from Louis Andriessen who developed (e.g. in *Workers Union* from 1975) the notion of ‘pitch contours’, basically free pitch, but the melodic shape (descending or ascending) is scored with the notated rhythm. With inevitable cacophony, if somewhat planned, in the final three pages of the score, I swapped from stepping down the delay time per page to a gradual descent from 100 milliseconds to zero. This brought back the initial idea of sliding through a delay continuum, starting at 100 milliseconds (indicative of the auditory-visual integration window mentioned by Lewald and Guski above [10]) going down through phasing effects and ending with no delay at all.

Page	Delay time	BPM Delay	Meter	BPM Score	Beats in 13 sec.	Bars per page	Remarks
0	5000	12	9	108	23.4	2.6	
1	4330	13.9	9	125	27.1	3.01	
2	3900	15.4	8	123	26.7	5.01	Dotted
3	3700	16.2	6	97	21	3.5	
4	3260	18.4	9	166	36	4	
5	3007	20	6	120	26	4.33	
6	2790	21.5	12	258	55.9	4.66	
7	2600	23.1	11	254	55	5	
8	2440	24.6	8	197	42.7	8.01	Dotted
9	2168	27.7	10	276	60	6	
10	1860	32.3	7	226	49	7	
11	1500	40	4	160	34.7	13.01	Dotted
12	1302	46.1	6	277	60	10	
13	1000	60	3	180	39	13	
14	766	78.3	2	157	34	17	
15	500	120	1	120	26	26	
16	250	240	1	240	52	52	
17	200	300	1	300	65	65	
18	100	600	1	600	130	130	
19	50	1200	1	1200	260	260	
20	Chaos						

Table 2. Spreadsheet to analyze delay times, BPM and meter for each page in the score.

4.4 Scrolling Score

Transferring the score from the notation module in the DAW (I used Cubase) to the scoreplayer was a challenge

and a considerable amount of editing was needed to fit the individual pages I created (one page for each step down in delay time) in one long *scroll*. After a first rehearsal, with the ensemble (who, needless to say, are very experienced with the scrolling score system), it became obvious that the combination of traditional rhythmic notation and the scrolling score did not allow for precise execution at higher tempos. But at this stage in the project there was no time to start from scratch. In rehearsal we did experiment with a click track, which would perhaps allow for a smoother execution, but would also require more rehearsal time. Additionally, playing with a click track on headphones can be unpleasant for performers and can also be audible to the audience in quieter parts.

When considering how this scrolling score shapes the performance ecology, synchronization is a key element. Using OSC, the score communicates with the MAX/MSP patch that realized the audio delay, and so synchronizing not just the performers but also the audio processing [11].

5. PERFORMANCES

The work was premiered at the Totally Huge New Music Festival in Perth, Western Australia in October 2017. The venue at the Perth Institute of Contemporary Arts has the layout of a traditional theater, and the set-up was adapted from the initial sketch (fig. 2), with the ‘pile of loudspeakers’ center stage, now more a stack than a pile (fig. 3).

Figure 3. Performance set-up at PICA, Perth 2017.

Figure 4. Concert at PICA, left to right Cat Hope, Lindsay Vickery, Aaron Wyatt, Tristen Parr, loudspeakers

and Stuart James. Out of shot, on the left is percussionist Louise Devenish. Photo: Bohdan Warchomij.

The centrality of, and the spotlights on the loudspeaker stack also became an interesting variation on the approach that ensemble decibel usually takes, with a loudspeaker near each performer (fig. 4).

Figure 5. Stage layout and loudspeaker set-up generally used by ensemble decibel.

During this first performance the WIFI router connecting the individual iPads in use by the performers crashed, or otherwise disconnected, which instantly turned the performance into an improvised version of the work. It left the audience, and the composer, somewhat confused about what they experienced, and the response was unsurprisingly lackluster. Consequentially, the recording of the performance was useless as a document, but luckily the ensemble agreed to recording a performance of the work in the studio. This new context for the work also allowed for a bypass of the tempo issue described above, with the final two pages of the score now printed out, making the execution easier and very much more precise.

In the podcast (see footnote 1) documenting both the concert and the studio recording, producer and presenter Stephen Adams describes the studio recording of the work as follows: “...with everything in sync you [got to] hear the strange temporal shifts in the relationship between the live players and the speaker stack [...] At first sounding far apart in time like two unconnected ensembles, then, in tighter, out of phase rhythms as the speaker delay shortened. And finally, the ensemble and speakers lining up with each other to produce what we casually call amplification. [...] a reminder that amplification is anything but an ordinary acoustic situation, the speakers in the room are effectively a whole other instrument, an electronic performer.”

The work was performed once more at the 2018 Australasian Computer Music Conference at the Western Australian Academy of Performance arts in Perth, again using a paper score for the problematic final pages. This performance was much better received and the intended effects were much easier to note, and commented upon by several audience members.

5.1 Outcomes

In answer to the research question raised above (how can I design a system to musically explore the contextualization realized by electroacoustic amplification?), the challenges to perform faster tempi at low delay times using the score player is a first outcome of this project. It is certainly of interest that, although perhaps this should not come as a surprise, that once the delay time is below 100 milliseconds (i.e. the final pages of the score) the execution of the score becomes a problem, and a different approach to the composition is required.

Another way of considering this challenge in the current approach is that the pages of the score scroll at the same speed, whereas a varying speed would allow for a reduction of the information density.

One way I have begun exploring is the using the so-called canvas mode in the score player application that allows the scrolling score to be used as a drawing surface using OSC commands.⁵ This would allow for experimentation with response time to instant cues, potentially allowing for more precision at greater tempos, and or, varying the scrolling speed.

6. FUTURE WORK

As mentioned above, my intention with this work is the realization of an experimental system that allows for more formal, decontextualized, exploration of the relation between instrument and loudspeaker. To realize that I will need to develop several iterations of this work's score. As indicated, improvements in the score need to be explored, but also different strategies to realizing the rhythmical synchronization between the interpreted score and the delayed sounds. In the version discussed in this paper tempo, meter and rhythmical possibilities were decided by choices made around the delay system. A next version could do the opposite where an accelerating composition, for instance using rhythmic modulation and complex meters, informs the changing delay times.

Currently a version for Disklavier is in preparation to be used in the more formal setting of a recording studio. This will create an environment for experimental exploration of the subtle changes in balance (between acoustic sound from the piano and amplified sound from the loudspeaker) in relation to subtle changes in delay time of the transduced sound. This could be a version of the work exploring specifically the domain between zero and 100 milliseconds of time delay. Using a Disklavier would fix the performance (and scoring) parameters while other conditions (visibility, relative level etc.) can be varied. Participants can be tasked with balancing the level of the transduced sound coming from the loudspeaker and the acoustic sound as produce by the piano. The aim of such experimentation is an increase of our knowledge on the practice of music creation, the subtleties of auditory visual integration, and, for instance, the different functions of sound amplification as set out by Emmerson.

⁵ <https://www.psi-borg.org/#canvas>

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] Wyatt, A., L. Vickery, and S. James. "Unlocking the Decibel ScorePlayer", in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Technologies for Music Notation and Representation -- TENOR'19*. 2019. Monash University.
- [2] Wyatt, A., et al. "Animated Music Notation on the iPad", in *Proceedings of ICMC*. 2013.
- [3] Cancino, J. P. and J. Mulder, "On Stockhausen's Solo(s): Beyond Interpretation." *Leonardo Music Journal* 28:13-18. https://doi.org/10.1162/lmj_a_01036.
- [4] Mulder, J. "The Loudspeaker as musical instrument", in *Proceedings of NIME 2010*, Sydney. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1177861>
- [5] Mulder, J., *Making things louder: amplified music and multimodality*, in *FASS2013*, University of Technology Sydney. <http://hdl.handle.net/10453/21903>.
- [6] Van Eck, C., "Between air and electricity: microphones and loudspeakers as musical instruments". 2017: Bloomsbury Publishing USA.
- [7] Emmerson, S., *Living electronic music*, 2007, Aldershot: Ashgate.
- [8] Mulder, J. "Sound Amplification Technology and the Acousmatic Experience", in *Proceedings of Systematic Musicology*, 2009, Ghent.
- [9] McCarthy, B., *Sound systems : design and optimization : modern techniques and tools for sound system design and alignment*, 1st ed. 2007, Oxford ; Burlington, MA: Focal.
- [10] Lewald, J. and R. Guski, "Auditory-visual temporal integration as a function of distance: no compensation for sound-transmission time in human perception". *Neuroscience Letters*, 2004. 357(2): p. 119-122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2003.12.045>

- [11] Masu, R., N. Do Nascimento Correia, and T. Romao, “NIME scores: a systematic review of how scores have shaped performance ecologies in NIME”, 2021.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1177861>